

Enhancing coastal resilience: AI-driven seasonal to multi-year water level predictions for the Texas Gulf Coast

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing rise in sea level over the last decade has substantially increased the frequency of coastal inundation episodes across regions such as the Texas Gulf coast. Nevertheless, presently, stakeholders lack the essential tools for adequate preparation in response to these events. To address this gap, our research introduces a multilayer perceptron model specifically designed to forecast water levels across various time scales, ranging from months to years. This model uses a unified signal derived from a refined analysis of historical tide gauge time series along the Texas coast. Our model goes beyond existing short-term and location-specific predictions by offering forecasts that span from seasonal to multi-year timescales, and cover the entire coastline. This extended outlook, provides coastal stakeholders and beach managers with the lead time needed to better plan and implement effective mitigation measures. This cutting-edge model, which could be adapted for other coastal regions, achieves a mean absolute error of less than 8 cm – a substantial improvement over the existing regional prediction tools, which have a variability of approximately ± 15 cm.

1. Introduction

Sea level rise is intensifying the frequency and severity of coastal inundation events worldwide, posing growing challenges to ocean and coastal management (Yang et al., 2014; Aucelli et al., 2017). Most existing prediction systems are restricted to short lead times — from hours to a few days — leaving limited room for proactive response by beach managers and emergency planners (Vitart and Robertson, 2018; White et al., 2017). In recent years, Seasonal to Multi-Year (S2MY) predictions have gained attention as a means to fill this gap, enabling more strategic and long-range coastal planning (White et al., 2017; Vitart et al., 2012; Nieves et al., 2021; Dusek et al., 2022).

The Texas Gulf Coast, home to some of the largest ports in the United States (Cox et al., 2002), is highly exposed to the impacts of sea level rise and land subsidence. Water level data for this region are primarily collected from tide gauges (TG) and satellite altimetry. While TG records date back to the early 1900s, they often suffer from gaps and station discontinuities. Conversely, satellite altimetry provides broader spatial coverage but with lower temporal resolution and limited accuracy near the shoreline (Adebisi et al., 2021). These limitations present significant challenges for long-lead water level forecasting in the Gulf of Texas (Qiao et al., 2023).

To date, regional S2MY prediction tools have largely relied on statistical extrapolations of historical trends. For example, current operational guidance in Texas is based on projecting RSLR trends along with interannual variability within a ± 15 cm envelope using past data from individual TG stations (NOAA Tides & Currents, 2023a). However, these tools do not account for complex climate signals or spatial generalization across locations with sparse or incomplete data.

Machine learning (ML) approaches have been applied to water level and wave forecasting tasks — primarily at short timescales — using techniques such as neural networks and support vector machines (Tissot et al., 2004; Muslim et al., 2020; Vicens-Miquel et al., 2024). However, to our knowledge, this is the first study to apply AI methods to predict seasonal to multi-year water levels for the Texas Gulf Coast. This work introduces a unified regional modeling strategy, using a common TG signal built from clustered stations, to capture broader climate-driven variability and support generalizable forecasts.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the potential of Artificial Intelligence — specifically a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model — to produce accurate S2MY water level predictions across the Texas coast. By modeling a unified regional signal, the goal is to

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Fig. 1. Geographical locations of the selected tide gauge stations used to generate the unified signal across the Texas Gulf coast region, over which we conducted analysis using both tide gauge and satellite datasets, determined using k-means clustering. The clustered region is highlighted in gray on the amended map. See Radin and Nieves (2024) for further details on the clustering analysis.

reduce reliance on individual station continuity and support real-time decision-making for coastal management.

This study makes four primary contributions. First, we propose and develop an MLP-based model tailored to predict water levels along the Texas Gulf Coast at seasonal to multi-year timescales, addressing the limitations of location-specific predictions and overfitting challenges. Second, the model is designed to achieve substantially lower forecast uncertainty compared to existing interannual variability tools, with the potential to reduce average errors below 8 cm—a significant improvement over the commonly accepted ± 15 cm range (NOAA Tides & Currents, 2023a). Third, we investigate the role of seasonal signals in prediction performance, offering insights into factors that shape long-term coastal water level variability. Finally, we demonstrate the model's potential as a real-time decision-support tool for coastal stakeholders, enhancing readiness for inundation-related risks through earlier and more localized warnings.

2. Materials and methods

This section begins with an in-depth exploration of the data utilized in this research, providing a comprehensive description of the datasets and the pre-processing techniques applied to enhance their suitability for the study. Following this, we provide a comprehensive description of the methodology employed to ensure accurate and reliable water level predictions.

2.1. Historical water levels

This research utilized two distinct datasets, encompassing TG and satellite data, for sea level analysis, extending until December 2022. Both data sources offer water level measurements, and their selection hinges on the research's specific demands. The datasets were analyzed over a clustered region encompassing nearly the entire Texas Gulf Coast

(depicted in Fig. 1). The study area was defined using a k-means clustering approach, a well-established unsupervised algorithm for identifying domains within the basin that exhibit coherent variability (see, for example, Meza-Padilla et al., 2019). This approach not only led to the delineation of the study area but also strengthened the hypothesis presented next, suggesting that our time series share comparable variability patterns relevant to the broader Texas Gulf Coast region. The k-means algorithm was specifically applied to NOAA's ocean temperature estimates (Oceanic and Administration, 2023) following Radin and Nieves (2024). In many cases, deriving localized variability regions from temperature measurements data, rather than satellite data, is preferred for various reasons, notably due to the availability of consistent long-term records. The technique involves iteratively assigning data points to cluster centroids to optimize variability, with robust results achieved by using median centroids, correlation distance, and multiple replicates. This process ultimately identifies 22 optimal clusters globally that align with established dynamical regions (Radin and Nieves, 2024), including a cluster for the Texas Gulf Coast region used for this study.

The monthly TG data (relative to the historic local Mean Sea Level, MSL, datum) is available from the NOAA Tides and Currents portal (NOAA Tides & Currents, 2023b,c), encompassing the timespan from January 1955 to present. To investigate water levels across the Texas Gulf coast, this study suggests generating a unified Texas signal. This approach allows for the creation of a predictive model capable of generating more comprehensive forecasts encompassing the entire region's coastline, as opposed to being limited to individual TG stations. This could be achieved by strategically selecting specific TG stations along the Texas coastline delineated by the clustered region. The selected stations comprise Sabine Pass, Port Mansfield, Galveston Pleasure Pier, Bob Hall Pier, Rockport, Port Isabel, Galveston Pier 21, and Freeport (as shown in Fig. 1). Consequently, the Texas common signal was created

Fig. 2. Water level time series of the tide gauge stations along the Texas Gulf coast. Each tide gauge station is represented by a distinct color as indicated in the figure legend, while the common signal is in dark blue.

by computing the mean and standard deviation across all individual stations after removing the respective TG's linear trends.

This detrending step was essential to focus the analysis on internal climate variability and interannual fluctuations, rather than long-term sea level rise. Importantly, it also removes the contributions from land subsidence, which can be substantially larger than the background rate of sea level rise and varies spatially along the Texas coast (Yarbrough et al., 2009). By removing the linear trend from each station, the resulting unified signal captures shared variability across the region while avoiding biases due to long-term or location-specific vertical land motion. This ensures that the model is trained on and predicts meaningful interannual variations rather than being influenced by the respective stations' long-term sea level rise (Church and White, 2011; Ponte, 2006).

Given the study's focus on seasonal-to-multi-year forecasting, we resampled the monthly tide gauge data to 3-month seasonal averages. This preprocessing is a widely used approach in climate and sea level studies to suppress the influence of short-term and high-frequency variability (Church and White, 2011; Dangendorf et al., 2014). These high-frequency components include astronomical tides, storm surges, and local wind variability, which typically operate at synoptic to intramonthly timescales (Ponte, 2006). As such, we did not apply explicit corrections for these short-term phenomena, since their contribution is largely smoothed out in seasonal means. Furthermore, removing these high-frequency drivers aligns with our modeling objective to capture lower-frequency variability relevant to seasonal-to-multi-year forecasting, while minimizing the influence of short-term noise (Church and White, 2011).

Additionally, data gaps were handled adaptively within the unified signal framework. For short gaps (e.g., hours to days), their influence on 3-month seasonal averages is minimal and has been shown in prior studies to not significantly alter regional trend estimates (Ray and Douglas, 2011). For longer gaps (≥ 3 months), we excluded the affected station from the seasonal mean computation at that time step and relied on valid data from the remaining stations. This strategy maintains robustness and ensures representativeness of the regional signal, particularly when working with sparse or heterogeneous station availability over long timeframes (Wöppelmann et al., 2009).

An essential pre-processing step involved resampling the monthly TG data into 3-month intervals (January, April, July, October). This adjustment was necessary to address temporal patterns and reduce noise.

The monthly data proved to be too noisy for capturing the longer-lived water-level fluctuations, which are more closely related with climate events. We selected January, April, July, and October as representative quarterly months to align with the Copernicus SLA dataset, enabling potential model integration or model comparisons. This resampling emphasizes seasonal-to-interannual patterns rather than short-term lunisolar variability, which is not the focus of this study. Fig. 2 illustrates the 3-month seasonal resampled TG data, emphasizing the consistency of water level oscillation patterns across TG stations along the Texas coast. This uniformity in oscillation patterns justifies the creation of the common Texas signal. Furthermore, the figure illustrates a noticeable upward trend in water levels, aligning with findings in current literature (Ponte et al., 2019). Consequently, as mentioned earlier, the dataset underwent detrending to emphasize relevant internal climate variations, ultimately leading to more accurate and interpretable predictions of water levels (Alsumaiei, 2020).

We conducted an additional analysis on daily sea level anomalies SLAs sourced from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). SLAs refer to the deviation in the height of water over the mean sea surface within a specific time and region. The dataset spans from January 1993 to June 2023 (Copernicus Marine Service, 2023). Calculated at a quarter-degree resolution relative to a twenty-year mean reference period (1993–2012), this dataset integrates annual mean sea level anomalies from all satellite missions. The data underwent meticulous corrections, including adjustments for instrumental drift and geophysical factors, facilitated by DUACS (Taburet et al., 2023). To ensure compatibility with the other datasets, we resampled the data onto a 3-month resolution grid and applied detrending procedures. Additionally, it is important to note that the analysis of altimetry-derived water level variability (discussed later) was conducted across the entire encompassing domain shown in Fig. 1, specifically using the median regional value for the delineated area.

While altimetry data may not align perfectly with TG measurements, especially in coastal regions where satellite altimetry faces challenges in accurately measuring sea level data within approximately 10 km from the coast (Benveniste et al., 2019), it still offers a reasonable representation of water levels, particularly on regional and climatic scales. Fig. 3 illustrates that both products capture similar oscillations, despite the differences in regional extension and the presence of local factors, such as subsidence (which was not analyzed in this study) (Haley et al., 2022; Qiao et al., 2023).

Fig. 3. Comparison of variations between the unified tide gauge signal and satellite data. The times series are displayed post-detrending, with interpolation applied using a 3-year window for enhanced visualization.

2.2. Supervised learning for future water levels

Here, we explore the implementation of supervised learning for predicting future water levels, employing an MLP architecture. The following details the model's design, hyperparameter tuning, and optimization steps to achieve accurate predictions in diverse scenarios.

An MLP is a specific type of artificial neural network characterized by multiple layers of interconnected neurons, with each layer being fully connected to the previous one. The selection of the MLP architecture was motivated by its ability to generalize effectively, particularly in scenarios with limited data (Taud and Mas, 2018). The fundamental components of an MLP encompass an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. These artificial neurons, also referred to as nodes or units, are responsible for processing information and transmitting it to the subsequent layer. The connections between these neurons possess associated weights that are fine-tuned during the training process (Taud and Mas, 2018; Bisong, 2019). Following an extensive tuning process of the model architecture using KerasTuner, a widely-used optimizer employing random search, we aim to determine an efficient configuration for the model hyperparameters. These hyperparameters include the number of hidden layers (ranging from 1 to 4), the batch size (from 32 to 512) and number of neurons (from 1 to 256) in the hidden layers, the learning rate (from 0.1 to 0.00001), the optimizer (Adam or RMSprop), and the loss function (Mean Square Error, or MSE) in the output layer of each model run. We also incorporated an early stopping criterion with a patience threshold of 35 and used L2 regularization (with a value of 0.0001) to prevent overfitting and ensure the generalization of our model. The setup identified, which involved a batch size of 512, the RMSprop optimizer, and a learning rate of 0.0001, resulted in a shallow MLP consisting of an input layer, one hidden layer with eight neurons using the sigmoid activation function, and an output layer. This streamlined model structure aligns with the dataset's size. Deeper architectures tended to result in overfitting, diminishing the model's ability to generalize and its overall performance.

Note that MLPs serve as predictors, and when combined with integrated backward sliding-window functionality, they enhance the model's ability to understand the varying temporal aspects (patterns and cycles) present in the time-series of sea level. In this context, the different input windows of inputs (ranging from the past 12 to 45 months) are treated as an hyperparameter, optimized by the KerasTuner. Adjusting the window size improves the model's ability to capture underlying dynamics across various time scales from short-term fluctuations to long-term trends, thus enhancing its predictive

capabilities. The corresponding expected outputs are examined over time, across different forecasting intervals. To ensure robust model generalization across diverse time frames, we implemented k-fold cross-validation with ten folds. These folds were created by dividing the data into training, testing, and validation sets, with each fold representing a distinct portion of the historical time series, thus encompassing various scenarios. After evaluating different partitioning strategies that varied from 70% to 85% for the training set, no notable distinctions were found. In cases with no significant differences, it is typically advantageous to opt for the largest training dataset, allowing the model to extract insights from a more extensive sample, crucial for operational models. Consequently, we adopted a partitioning scheme that allocated 85% of the dataset for training, 5% for validation, and 10% for testing, while ensuring three continuous temporal blocks to mitigate temporal autocorrelations. Note that each fold underwent five rounds of training and testing repetitions. This helped capture the spread of the model's calibration and enhance the overall model's robustness, resulting in fifty experiments for each forecasting interval (totaling 600 experiments). The model's output consisted of water level predictions for specific forecasting times, using the best-performing sliding window in each case. This selection is crucial for accurate forecasting, as it accounts for varying temporal patterns and cycles in different datasets and tasks. The entire workflow of this research is depicted in Fig. 4.

To evaluate our predictions, we employed the coefficient of determination (R^2) derived from the MSE loss function, in conjunction with the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), which indicates the extent of prediction accuracy. While R^2 offers insight into the model's ability to explain the variability in the data (with an R^2 value of 1 indicating perfect prediction), MAE focuses on the average magnitude of errors between predicted and actual values. According to Asuero et al. (2006), an R^2 value between 0.25 and 0.48 indicates a moderate correlation, while values between 0.49 to 0.79 signify high correlations. When employed together, these metrics provide a comprehensive understanding of the model's accuracy and explanatory power.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (2)$$

where y_i and \hat{y}_i are the observed Texas Gulf unified signal from TG data and the model prediction from this signal, respectively.

Fig. 4. This figure presents an overview of the workflow from data preparation to prediction. Tide gauge and satellite data are detrended and resampled to 3-month intervals. A unified tide gauge signal is created, and a multi-layer perceptron model is trained using sliding windows to generate seasonal to multi-year water level forecasts. Model performance is evaluated using mean absolute error and R-squared metrics.

3. Results

This section presents the main results of the model performance evaluation using the predefined metrics. The findings include: (i) results for the tide gauge-based model, (ii) performance comparisons with and without seasonal cycle removal, and (iii) a case study using satellite altimetry input.

3.1. Model performance using tide gauge data

Our MLP-based model forecasts water levels, indicating whether the water level will increase or decrease in the upcoming months or years. These predictions hold significant value as they serve as indicators for anticipating coastal inundation.

As detailed in section 2.2, time series forecasts are generated by all models across various forecast lead times, using the mean outcomes obtained from five repeated runs for each k-fold. These results are presented in Table 1. For illustration purposes, we display results from one representative fold (k-fold = 1), which covers the most recent testing years. The model with median performance among five repetitions is shown in Fig. 5.

3.2. Effect of seasonal cycle removal

Table 2 shows results after removing the seasonal cycle using NOAA monthly means. MAE deteriorates for most lead times as well as when comparing average performance across all lead times, which decreases from 6.9 cm (0.4 cm standard deviation) to 8.7 cm (1.2 cm). MAEs across lead times were averaged for this comparison as the performance deteriorates only slowly with lead time as further discussed below. The difference in R^2 values is less clear although the average R^2 across lead times decreases from 0.5 (0.1) to 0.4 (0.3).

3.3. Satellite altimetry case study

The model was also tested using only altimetry-based sea level satellite altimetry. Table 3 and Fig. 6 summarize the results. Contrary to the results after removing the seasonal cycle using tide gauge averages, the removal of the altimetry-based signal leads to lower MAE, the lowest of the three methods with an average MAE across lead times decreasing from 6.9 cm (0.4 cm) to 3.1 cm (0.5 cm). The R^2 values are similar to the other two cases although with less variability across lead times than after removing the tide gauge based averages.

Fig. 5. The time series of water level predictions, specifically covering the final months/years of the record in this case. These predictions, extending from 3 to 36 months in forecast times, consistently align with the unified tide gauge signal. Visual comparisons are depicted with predictions in dark blue (Predicted) and the observational tide gauge data (OBS TG) in light blue. The model’s performance, assessed using mean absolute error and R-squared (embedded in the graphs), indicates favorable results. The subsequent numbers denote the selected sliding window size chosen for each respective forecasting period (in months): 21, 9, 9, 9, 9, 21, 9, 21, 21, 21, and 21.

Table 1

Performance metrics for our multi-layer perceptron model, computed with the unified tide gauge signal as input. The mean values across all k-folds are reported, following the averaging of five repetitions for each fold. The efficiency of the predictive model in forecasting water levels is assessed through the square root of the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Mean absolute error (MAE). These metrics are evaluated across diverse forecasting intervals, ranging from 3 to 36 months.

Forecasting time (Months)	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36
MAE (cm)	6.6	6.2	6.3	6.7	6.9	7.2	6.7	7.0	7.1	7.6	6.7	7.5
R^2	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4

4. Discussion

This section discusses the performance of our MLP model across different configurations and input sources. We discuss the results obtained from (i) the full unified tide gauge signal, (ii) the seasonally

detrended version, and (iii) the satellite altimetry-based configuration. Performance is assessed across various forecast lead times, focusing on accuracy and robustness, and comparison with existing methodologies.

Among the three, the model using the full unified TG signal consistently produced the best results. It achieved a mean absolute error of

Table 2

As in Table 1, but with additional preprocessing applied to the tide gauge dataset to remove the seasonal cycle.

Forecasting time (Months)	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36
MAE (cm)	9.0	9.1	6.6	6.7	9.3	9.5	9.2	7.5	9.5	10.7	8.7	8.7
R ²	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.1

Table 3

As in Table 1, but with satellite altimetry-based sea level data as input in the multi-layer perceptron model.

Forecasting time (Months)	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36
MAE (cm)	2.7	2.7	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.7	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.8	3.9	3.9
R ²	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2

Fig. 6. As in Fig. 5, but with satellite altimetry-based sea level data as input in the MLP model. In this case, the chosen sliding window sizes for each forecasting interval are as follows: 15, 15, 15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 15, 14, and 13.

less than 7 cm for lead times up to 15 months and under 8 cm for forecasts extending to 36 months—representing a significant improvement over the ± 15 cm uncertainty envelope used in current NOAA operational tools for interannual forecasting in the region (NOAA Tides & Currents, 2023c). Although no previous studies to our knowledge have applied AI to seasonal-to-multi-year (S2MY) water level prediction for the Texas Gulf Coast, our results demonstrate superior performance relative to the existing NOAA approach based on interannual variability. Specifically, our method reduces the forecast uncertainty envelope by nearly 50%. This highlights the potential of machine learning methods — particularly MLPs using unified signals — to deliver more accurate and actionable predictions for long-term coastal planning, even in data-sparse settings.

The R^2 values for this model range from 0.4 to 0.6 across all lead times, demonstrating stable alignment with observed water levels even at extended horizons. This suggests the model is capable of capturing large-scale seasonal and climate-related signals that evolve more slowly than short-term variability, as also noted in the long-term trend detection literature (Ponte et al., 2019; Church and White, 2011).

An interesting observation is the relatively small differences in predictions across lead times. These variations stem from the distinct historical input lengths and dynamics used for each forecast period. As expected, the magnitude of rare, extreme oscillations tends to be underrepresented due to their limited presence in the training data. Nevertheless, the model effectively captures most water level fluctuations, including peak interannual variability months. This consistency is further supported by the extremely low standard deviation (less than 1 mm) across five training repetitions, which is characteristic of shallow MLP architectures and enhances confidence in the model's reliability.

During model selection, we experimented with several AI architectures, including RNN and LSTM, but found that MLP consistently outperformed them. This outcome is explained by the relatively small sample size, fewer than 200 monthly observations, which poses challenges for sequence-based models that typically require longer time series to generalize effectively. Similar findings have been reported in the literature, where shallow architectures are shown to perform better in small-to-moderate data regimes (Muslim et al., 2020). Transformers were excluded from consideration due to their even greater data demands and computational overhead, which are not well aligned with the dataset size in this study. MLP architectures, known for their reliability in small-sample regimes, proved to be the most effective for our purposes. As the primary focus of this work is not to compare neural architectures, but rather to explore different sources of predictive signals (e.g., tide gauge vs. satellite altimetry) and forecast configurations (e.g., seasonal signal kept or removed), we present only the best-performing MLP model in the main results.

It is important to note that while our MLP model effectively captures seasonal to multi-year variability, its capacity to resolve longer-term climate oscillations — such as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO), or the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO) — is limited. This is due in part to the small size of the training dataset and the absence of explicit climate mode indices as input features, as has been emphasized in previous work (Ponte et al., 2019). The MLP architecture, although well-suited for the data volume in this study, is not specifically designed to extract structured low-frequency variability from long climate records. Additionally, the time span of usable tide gauge data (70 years) may be insufficient to represent multiple full cycles of multidecadal variability, which constrains the model's ability to generalize such patterns. Future extensions of this work could incorporate external climate predictors (e.g., Niño 3.4, AMO index, or ERA5 reanalysis variables) to improve representation of these phenomena and test their influence on regional sea level evolution.

Contrary to expectations, removing the average seasonal cycle led to a noticeable decline in performance. MAE values deteriorated across

most lead times. This suggests that seasonal signals embed meaningful information that should be preserved during training, rather than treated as noise. Similar conclusions were drawn by Alsumaiei (2020), who found that filtering periodic components can reduce forecast accuracy in groundwater models and other long-memory hydrologic systems. Our findings emphasize the importance of retaining periodic water level fluctuations to capture meaningful interannual structure.

In the satellite altimetry-based sea level case study, the model achieved the lowest MAE values across all lead times, indicating strong predictive skill in capturing regional sea level variability and confirming the value of satellite-derived SLA signals in regional forecasting (Copernicus Marine Service, 2023). However, R^2 values were more variable beyond 6-month forecasts, likely due to the shorter record length and limitations in capturing coastal dynamics (Benveniste et al., 2019). These findings align with previous studies highlighting satellite altimetry's challenges in nearshore zones but also its strength in detecting regional sea level patterns over open water (Adebisi et al., 2021). Notably, the improved performance at shorter lead times is partially attributed to the smaller amplitude of sea level fluctuations captured via altimetry (see Fig. 3), which may reduce error variance in the short term. These results underscore the utility of altimetric datasets for short- to medium-term water level predictions and suggest that as longer, higher-quality records become available, their contribution to multi-year forecasting could significantly increase. This experiment demonstrates the valuable role of satellite-based observations in enhancing regional forecasting capabilities and provides a foundation for future work exploring their integration with tide gauge data and external climate predictors to further improve accuracy and spatial generalization.

Overall, our results show that the proposed MLP-based framework offers a robust, generalizable solution for S2MY sea level forecasting. By comparing three different model configurations and contextualizing the findings within prior literature, we demonstrate that shallow ML architectures — when paired with carefully pre-processed inputs — can outperform conventional forecasting tools. This holds promise for improving coastal resilience planning, particularly in data-sparse or high-risk regions.

Moreover, our approach differs from traditional physics-based or statistical forecasting methods and delivers substantial improvements in both predictive accuracy and lead time. To our knowledge, no prior studies have implemented multi-year water level forecasting along the Texas Gulf Coast using machine learning, highlighting the novelty and practical relevance of this work. The resulting model functions as a scalable, real-time decision-support tool for coastal managers, offering early warnings that can inform mitigation strategies for inundation risks. The integration of unified tide gauge signals, seasonal analysis, and alternate data sources provides a flexible foundation for future modeling efforts, and advances the potential of data-driven approaches in coastal forecasting and resilience.

5. Conclusion

This study introduces an AI-based seasonal-to-multi-year water level forecasting framework tailored to the Texas Gulf Coast. Unlike single-station models, our approach leverages a unified tide gauge signal across the region, enabling robust, scalable predictions that support informed mitigation planning up to 36 months in advance.

Quantitatively, the model achieves a mean absolute error of < 7 cm for lead times up to 15 months, and < 8 cm for up to 36 months. These results outperform the ± 15 cm uncertainty range currently used in operational interannual forecasting tools for Texas, representing a substantial improvement in predictive accuracy. In addition, the model maintains average R^2 values of approximately 0.45 at shorter leads and demonstrates skillful alignment with observed variability even at extended horizons.

Importantly, we find that retaining the full values of the average sea levels, without removing the long term seasonal cycle as measured by tide gauges, significantly improves model performance, highlighting the predictive value of the measured periodic components in water level signals. Our analysis also indicates that using gridded satellite altimetry-based sea level as input is feasible, particularly for short lead times, though, so far, it remains limited by shorter data records and lower amplitude variability. These findings demonstrate the potential for broader applications in data-sparse regions.

We acknowledge that the current framework is limited to 36-month forecasts. This boundary reflects a data-driven constraint: while our tide gauge record spans nearly 70 years (1955–2022), extending lead times beyond 36 months would require a substantially longer dataset to ensure robust model training, validation, and testing—particularly under best practices such as k-fold cross-validation and temporal splits. Moreover, predictions beyond this range enter the domain of long-term climate projections, which involve different assumptions and methodologies not suitable for the current machine learning approach. Another limitation of this study is that we did not perform a detailed error analysis at the individual station, seasonal, or extreme-event level. The heterogeneous and incomplete nature of tide gauge records across the region prevents a consistent per-station evaluation, and the study's scope was focused on seasonal-to-multi-year variability rather than extremes. Future work could address this by incorporating more complete or higher-resolution datasets, enabling station-level assessments and extending the framework to capture extreme-event dynamics.

It is also important to note that wind and current patterns play a key role in short-term and synoptic water level variability along the Texas Gulf Coast (e.g., storm surges, daily to weekly fluctuations, or along-shore current shifts). While such drivers are critical for short-term predictions, our seasonal-to-multi-year framework is not designed to explicitly capture transient events of this kind. Instead, the unified tide gauge signal inherently reflects the integrated, low-frequency influence of persistent wind regimes and regional current variability over time. Incorporating explicit oceanographic and meteorological forcings—such as wind stress fields, sea-level pressure, or Loop Current indices—could potentially improve both model performance and interpretability, as demonstrated in recent studies linking circulation features to subseasonal-to-seasonal sea level variability (Shinoda et al., 2023). However, doing so would substantially increase input dimensionality and data requirements and was beyond the scope of this study. Future extensions could explore integrating such physical drivers to assess their added value for multi-year forecasting applications.

Looking forward, future work could enhance model performance and generalizability by incorporating additional climate-relevant inputs such as NOAA wind fields, or sea-level pressure. The model's demonstrated robustness and low inter-run variability (<1 mm standard deviation across training repetitions) provide a solid foundation for such extensions.

Ultimately, this study offers a novel, practical AI-based tool for medium-range coastal inundation forecasting. Its successful deployment in the Texas Gulf Coast highlights its promise for broader application in other vulnerable coastal regions seeking to improve climate resilience and advance ocean and coastal management.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marina Vicens-Miquel: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Cristina Radin:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Veronica Nieves:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Philippe E. Tissot:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

All data discussed in the paper is available in the following GitHub repository: https://github.com/conrad-blucher-institute/S2MY_WaterLevelsPredictions.

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